

Working paper: Torsion-shear behaviour at the corrugated interlocking joints

Mechanical behaviour of an assemblage of rigid or deformable blocks is highly dependent on the shape and location of the joints between the assemblage components. Non-planar joints can interlock to adjacent blocks and improve their sliding or rotational resistance.

An interlocking block with corrugated faces can be seen as a main body with some projections on its faces called locks. If the locks and the main body are rigid enough, the block is failed only when the locks lose their connection with the main body. In this case, the mechanical behaviour of an interlocking joint not only depends on the frictional properties of the contacts between two blocks, but also on the mechanical properties of the contact interface between each lock and the main body.

This research work specifically studies the mechanical properties of this interface, considered made of cohesive material, when subjected to tangential forces. To this aim, the ultimate torsion-shear resistances of the contact subjected to the tangential force with different eccentricities with respect to the contact centroid are found, using numerical, analytical and experimental approaches.

The numerical approach is an extension of the concave, convex and corrected concave formulations elaborated in [1] for conventional planar joints.

The analytical approach is based on the discrete element method using 3DEC software [2].

The experimental investigation is a novel physical test to study the torsion-shear behaviour of interlocking joints as an alternative to the European Standard test [3].

The results given by the three approaches are extensively compared to each other for two samples with different material properties.

The experimental test was carried out at the Laboratory of the Department of Structures for Engineering and Architecture (DiSt) of the University of Napoli Federico II (Italy), jointly with Prof. C. Ceraldi and Arch. L. Argiento.

The analytical investigation was executed in collaboration with Prof. K. Bagi, from Structural Mechanics, Budapest University of Technology and Economics.

[1] Casapulla, C. and Maione A. (2018). Modelling the dry-contact interface of rigid blocks under torsion and combined loading: concavity vs. convexity formulation. *International Journal of Non-Linear Mechanics*, 99: 86-96

[2] Hart, R., Cundall, P.A. and Lemos, J. (1988). Formulation of a three-dimensional distinct element model-Part II. Mechanical calculations for motion and interaction of a system composed of many polyhedral blocks. *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences and Geomechanics*, 1988, 25(3): 117–125.

[3] UNI EN 1052-3 (2007). *Methods of test for masonry - Part 3: Determination of initial shear strength*.

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LVDT to measure displacement

Load cell to measure force

Fixing the frame to the stand against sliding

Electric hydraulic jack

Fixing the block to the wooden board against sliding

Fixing the wooden board to the upper support against sliding

Fixing the block to the upper support against rotation

